

Ultramicro Estimation of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} with Alizarin Red-S Using D.M.E.-Mercury Pool Electrode System

S. C. LAVALE and K. S. PITRE

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar-470 008

Manuscript received 24 March 1981, revised 23 November 1981, accepted 30 March 1983

Alizarin Red-S has been employed as a reagent for amperometric titrations of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} in aqueous and partially non-aqueous media. The titrations have been performed at pH 4.5 in acetate buffer and $\mu=0.1$. Thus, small quantities of La^{3+} (0.6945 to 4.8615 mg) and Ce^{3+} (0.7006 to 4.9042 mg) are amperometrically determined using Alizarin Red-S as a complexing agent with an error less than $\pm 0.53\%$. Titrations are not hampered by the presence of large amount of K^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Ti^+ , NH_4^+ , Cl^- , ClO_4^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- and CH_3COO^- ions. The mean deviation and standard deviation in case of La^{3+} vs ARS are found to be 0.073% and 0.096% and in case of Ce^{3+} vs ARS are 0.083% and 0.116%, respectively. Experimental data and calculated statistical data confirm high accuracy, precision and confidence of the procedure developed.

ALIZARIN and its derivatives are of unusual importance in complexometric studies. The use of Alizarin Red-S (a sodium salt of 1,2-dihydroxy anthraquinone-3-sulphonic acid) in spectrophotometric determination of metal ions has been discussed¹⁻⁸. However, the formation of lake by ARS in spectrophotometric work sometimes leads to a wrong stoichiometric ratio of metal : ligand because of suspensions and not true solution, of the complexes. The spectrophotometric method is not suitable where precipitation occurs, nor can it be used at the close proximity of the wave length of absorption of the complex and the ligand. These difficulties were circumvented by using amperometric technique. In the present paper we report the results of amperometric determination of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} with ARS using d.m.e. as an indicator electrode. The effect of interfering ions has also been studied using the procedure.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR quality. La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} solutions were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Riedel) or $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) in required volume of double distilled water. These solutions were standardised by conventional titrimetric procedure⁹.

The solution of Alizarin-Red S was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of the reagent (B.D.H.) in double distilled water, and standardised by the procedure of Larson and Hirozawa⁸. Amperometric titrations were performed on manually operated polarograph with multiflex galvanometer (sens. 8.10×10^9 amp/div) using d.m.e. as an indicator electrode and mercury pool as reference electrode. The capillary used for d.m.e. had a m value of 2.3733

mg/sec at a drop time 3 sec in air-free 0.1 M potassium chloride at 41 cm effective height of mercury column ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$). An Elico digital pH meter (model LI-120) was used for measuring pH of the test solutions.

A number of solutions containing calculated amounts of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} (in 10 ml volume) in acetate buffer were prepared for titrations. 0.1 M KCl was used as a supporting electrolyte. Titrations of these solutions were carried out at an applied voltage of -0.7 V vs mercury pool.

Results and Discussion

The current voltage behaviour of ARS has been studied⁷. ARS gives a well defined reduction wave in 0.1 M KCl and acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer at pH 4.5 with $E_{1/2} = -0.6$ V vs mercury pool. The height of diffusion current is proportional to the concentration of ARS. An aliquot of the metal solution (La^{3+} or Ce^{3+}) was taken into a titration cell in which the requisite amounts of supporting electrolyte and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer were added and diluted to a definite volume i.e., 10 ml. The plateau potential of the polarogram for ARS i.e., -0.7 V vs mercury pool (at which La^{3+} or Ce^{3+} do not give any diffusion current) was applied. The current was noted on adding the standard solution of ARS (pH=4.5) dropwise from 1 cm³ semi-micro burette. On plotting galvanometer reading after necessary volume correction⁸ against the titrant volume, a reversed L shaped curve was obtained. The end point indicated a Metal to ARS ratio of 1 : 2 which is in good agreement with the results reported in literature^{9,10}. Similar results were observed by choosing ARS as titrate and La^{3+} or Ce^{3+} as titrant (other conditions remaining the same), but an L shaped curve was obtained in this

case. It was also observed that each of these titrations can be performed in 25% ethanol medium which may be fruitful for the estimation of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} in compounds or ores soluble in partially ethanol medium.

The data in Tables 1 and 2 clearly indicate that this method is successfully applicable for the estimation of La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} upto microgram level with an error less than $\pm 0.53\%$. The mean deviation and standard deviation in case of La^{3+} vs ARS are 0.073% and 0.096%, respectively and for Ce^{3+} vs ARS are 0.083% and 0.116%, respectively.

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF La^{3+} WITH ALIZARIN RED-S, AT -0.7 V vs MERCURY POOL, $\mu=0.1$; $\text{pH}=4.5 \pm 0.02$

Sl. No.	Approximate molarity <i>M</i>	Amount of La^{3+}		% error
		Taken mg	Found mg	
1.	5.0×10^{-4}	0.6945	0.6917	-0.40
2.	1.0×10^{-3}	1.3890	1.3836	-0.38
3.	1.5×10^{-3}	2.0835	2.0940	+0.58
4.	2.0×10^{-3}	2.7780	2.7706	-0.27
5.	2.5×10^{-3}	3.4725	3.4846	+0.34
6.	3.0×10^{-3}	4.1670	4.1768	+0.23
7.	3.5×10^{-3}	4.8615	4.8464	-0.31

TABLE 2—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ce^{3+} WITH ARS, AT -0.7 V vs MERCURY POOL, $\mu=0.1$; $\text{pH}=4.5 \pm 0.02$

Sl. No.	Approximate molarity <i>M</i>	Amount of Ce^{3+}		% error
		Taken mg	Found mg	
1.	5.0×10^{-4}	0.7006	0.6981	-0.35
2.	1.0×10^{-3}	1.4012	1.4065	+0.37
3.	1.5×10^{-3}	2.1018	2.1069	+0.24
4.	2.0×10^{-3}	2.8024	2.7920	-0.37
5.	2.5×10^{-3}	3.5030	3.5196	+0.47
6.	3.0×10^{-3}	4.2036	4.1815	-0.52
7.	3.5×10^{-3}	4.9042	4.9808	+0.52

Study of the effect of diverse ions :

For interference studies, known amounts of foreign ions were added to a definite amount of metal ion (La^{3+} or Ce^{3+}) and the metal was titrated following the procedure described above. The titration of La^{3+} or Ce^{3+} is not in any way hampered by the presence of different amount of foreign ions as shown in Table 3. It is further observed that more than 100 folds of NH_4^+ , Cl^- , ClO_4^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- and CH_3COO^- ions do not interfere. However, small amount of CO_3^{2-} , Ag^+ , Pb^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , VO_3^{3-} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and MoO_4^{2-} ions interfered appreciably.

TABLE 3—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF La^{3+} AND Ce^{3+} WITH ARS IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS
Metal taken $\text{La}^{3+}=1.3890$ mg ; $\text{Ce}^{3+}=1.4012$ mg

Diverse ion added	La^{3+} Found (mg)	% error	Ce^{3+} Found (mg)	% error
K^+ (195 mg)	1.3818	-0.55	1.4087	+0.53
Na^+ (115 mg)	1.3785	-0.75	1.3952	-1.14
Mg^{2+} (48.6 mg)	1.3997	+0.77	1.4065	+0.87
Zn^{2+} (24.3 mg)	1.3836	-0.38	1.4107	+0.67
Tl^+ (15.3 mg)	1.3782	-0.77	1.4185	+1.23
Sn^{2+} (11.86 mg)	1.3920	+0.21	1.3958	-0.38
Cd^{2+} (11.24 mg)	1.3854	-0.25	1.3928	-0.59
Hg^{2+} (10 mg)	1.4015	+0.89	1.4128	+0.79
Se^{4+} (8.94 mg)	1.4058	+1.20	1.3937	-0.53
Te^{4+} (9.19 mg)	1.3773	-0.84	1.3955	-0.40

The figures within parenthesis show the amount of foreign ion added.

Conclusions :

(1) La^{3+} and Ce^{3+} can be estimated upto microgram quantities with ARS using amperometric procedure with an error less than $\pm 0.53\%$.

(2) The stoichiometry of complex metal : ARS is found to be 1 : 2 amperometrically.

(3) The same titrimetric procedure can be adopted in 25% ethanol medium, which may be fruitful for the estimation of La^{3+} or Ce^{3+} in compounds or ores soluble in partially ethanol medium.

(4) The relative mean deviation and standard deviation in case of La^{3+} vs ARS is found to be 0.073% and 0.096%, respectively and for Ce^{3+} vs ARS is 0.083% and 0.116%, respectively. The observed data and the calculated statistical data, indicate high accuracy, precision and confidence of the method.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S. C. L.) is grateful to U. G. C., New Delhi for a Teacher Fellowship. The authors also thank the Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar for facilities.

References

1. A. K. MUKERJI and A. K. DRY, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1958, 31, 521.

LAVALE & PITRE : ULTRAMICRO ESTIMATION OF La^{3+} AND Ce^{3+} WITH ALIZARIN RED-S ETC.

2. I. S. MUSTAFIN and E. A. KOSHKOVSKAYA, *Zhur. Obsch. Khim.*, 1956, **26**, 2981.
3. W. R. ROBERT, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1820.
4. S. K. BANERJI and A. K. DEY, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 357.
5. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid", D. Van Nostrand Co, Inc., 1957, pp. 174, 181.
6. E. M. LARSON and S. T. HIROZAWA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1956, **3**, 198.
7. N. H. FURMAN and K. G. STONE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **71**, 3055.
8. J. T. STOCK, "Amperometric Titrations", R. E. Krieger Pub. Co., Huntington, New York, 1975, p. 7.
9. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4744.
10. J. H. YOU and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.